

3D Mobile Robot Localization Aided by Point Cloud Keypoint Features and Three-Dimensional Localization (KEFT)

Vinicio Rosas-Cervantes¹, Soon-Geul Lee²

¹ Department of Mechanical Engineering, Kyung Hee University,
Yongin, Gyeonggi, South Korea (viniciorosas@hotmail.es)

² Department of Mechanical Engineering, Kyung Hee University,
Yongin, Gyeonggi, South Korea (sglee@khu.ac.kr)* Corresponding author

Abstract: The present paper, propose an algorithm for 3D mobile robot localization, based on kinematics analysis combined with point cloud treatment. The Scale Invariant Feature Transform (SIFT) Keypoints in combination with the Iterative Closest Points (ICP) and the terrain inclination achieve an efficient robot mapping and localization. Along two laser scans, the surface inclination aids to robot local localization, these localization results are the initial robot coordinates. The ICP algorithm overlaps the Keypoints obtained from the point cloud, reconstructing the global map. The localization time reduced significantly, due the algorithm proposed works with Keypoints rather the entire point cloud as conventionally in previous studies. The experiment shows time reduction and accuracy improvement for Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM) on the uneven surface.

Keywords: Mobile robot; Path planning; Obstacle avoidance; Feature recognition; 3D Mapping.

1. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays the application trend of the mobile robotics is oriented to perform activities as delivery rather than actual mapping. As an example, the Commercial robots created by Starship Company [1]. Obtaining a precise localization with a low cost is vital for a successful robot performance. Localization still is a daunting task; several approaches attempt to reduce the operational cost, energy consumption and running time. The Iterative Closest Point (ICP) [2], a conventional solution compares two point clouds and obtains a transformation matrix. This method widely employed in scenarios compose by 2D obstacles. Moreover, 3D localization requires a large point cloud. The ICP algorithm recreates a visual odometry map [3-4] due the point cloud is an unorganized set of points. Obtaining a match of every point cloud is time demanding for real-time implementation. Recreating a map using ICP consumes at least 30 seconds for matching two different point clouds. This time is not suitable for real-time applications. Besides, the point cloud concatenation is not precise. An alternative solution for a faster map recreation and time improvement is geometric point cloud analysis. Using the point's distribution localizes features [5] and classify them consecutively [6]. As a consequence, the output point cloud resolution improves. Moreover, this point cloud treatment is acceptable for offline application; the computation time is 120 seconds. This point cloud treatment shows good results with short point clouds (150 000 points). For this paper, the selected sensor for environment recognition is a Kinect Camera. This sensor grants an environment recognition at low price compare with the three-dimensional Lidar Sensor. The algorithm determines the SIFT Keypoints in every point cloud acquired by the robot. Follow by an ICP application over the detected Keypoints, obtaining a transformation matrix. The transformation matrix aids to estimate the robot position. The IMU sensor estimates robot the displacement in the three axes (X, Y, Z). Finally combined the IMU estimation with the transformation matrix, the algorithm obtains the robot positioning in the global and local frame.

2. LOCALIZATION AIDED BY UNEVEN SURFACE

2.1 Coordinate Reference Frame

The experiment set up consists of a Turtlebot equipped by a Kobuki Robot, a laptop running Ubuntu Linux 14.0, and a Microsoft Kinect camera as shows the Fig. 1. The robot connected to a master station via a Wi-Fi router, the master station is working with Matlab, using the Robotics Tool Box 1.4. Matlab allows communication with the Robotics Operating System (ROS) installed on the robot laptop.

The experiment coordinate systems are the following: the world coordinate (x, y, z) , the robot coordinate (x_b, y_b, z_b) and the Kinect camera coordinate (x_1, y_1, z_1) . The world coordinate (x, y, z) located at the initial position, has a tangential plane to the soil. The robot coordinate has the orthogonal axis located in the middle point of the rear robot axis. The axis x_b is always parallel to the robot velocity. The axis z_b is vertical to the robot plane. Finally, the axis direction for the Kinect camera is coincident with the robot axis.

2.2 Surface inclination aided localization

A university corridor and a ramp recreated the experiment scenario. The ramp simulates the uneven surface, and it has a $\alpha=10^\circ$ inclination. The uneven surface aids to localize the robot, combining the sensor data obtained from the odometer and accelerometer. The robot trajectory path represented by the red line, the origin is O_b .

Fig. 1. Experiment Coordinate System

3. EXPERIMENT AND RESULTS

The experiment executed in one university corridor. Two scenarios considered, the first using the ramp, and the second without the ramp. This setup allows comparing the precision of the two algorithms: Keypoint Features aid Three-Dimensional Localization (KEFT) and ICP-SLAM, for even an uneven surface. The Kobuki robot used for the experiment integrates an Inertia Measurement Sensor (IMU). The IMU sensor measures the roll, pitch, yaw angles and the angular velocities $\omega_{x_b}, \omega_{y_b}, \omega_{z_b}$. The robot encoders provides the coordinate forward speed V_{x_b} . The V_{y_b} and V_{z_b} with respect the robot coordinate, considered without slip. The scanning frequency is every 50 cm. For the point cloud processing, the ICP-SLAM and the KEFT algorithm applied to the same region where the robot stop and scan. The point cloud processing allows to calculate the robot localization. The robot moves with a linear speed of 0.05 m/s. The sampling period is $\Delta t=1s$. The

robot has enough time for point cloud acquisition and collecting information from the odometry sensors. Fig. 2 shows the scanned map where the experiment took place. The scanning frequency was 20 seconds, being faster than the methods described in the introduction section.

Fig. 2. Mapping using Keypoint Features Method.

The first scan took with the robot stopped, the second scan after a $\Delta t = 20s$, and so on. The first scan aligned with the continuous scan, recreate the scenario. This aligning process repeated in a loop generates a transformation matrix. This matrix works as a reference to calculate the robot localization. The scanning convergence period is less than 5 seconds. The error estimation concerning each axis is less than 0.3 meter according to the Table 1. For ICP-SLAM, the experiment shows a significant variation towards the reference marks, on an uneven surface. The KEFT algorithm provides a 4 seconds faster localization than the ICP-SLAM, for both scenarios: even and uneven surface.

Table 1. Consuming time comparison.

No.	Test Distance	Method	Consuming time for localization	Matching time	Total Time
1	5 m	KEFT	0.1 (s) \times 5 times= 0.5(s)	0.6 (s) \times 5 times= 3(s)	3.5 (s)
2	5 m	ICP-SLAM	0.3 (s) \times 5 times=1.5(s)	1.2 (s) \times 5 times= 6(s)	7.5 (s)

Table 2. Error Measurement in Uneven Surface

Method	KEFT	ICP based SLAM
Error (m)		
Mean x-axis	0.4688	0.3625
Variance x-axis	0.7823	1.1265
Mean y-axis	0.7343	0.6811
Mean z-axis	-0.0812	-0.2974
Variance z-axis	0.0464	0.06688
Mean Distance	0.085	0.0209
Variance Distance	0.0017	0.0018

4. CONCLUSIONS

This paper introduces a mobile robot localization algorithm, combining SIFT Keypoints and 3D terrain inclination, for mapping and localization in indoor environment. The experimental values obtained, validate the proposed technique that improves the processing time for localization and mapping. Furthermore, obtaining

a better accuracy than the traditional Iterative Closest Point (ICP). Future work will focus on obtaining an even faster response on the Keypoint feature detection and extend this algorithm to outdoor larger areas.

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